

ISSUES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF TERMS RELATED TO THE RAILWAY SECTOR IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract: *this article analyzes the process of working with the terminology of the railway sector in the educational process by future specialists. The classification of terms related to the railway industry and the procedure for its application are highlighted. English railway terminology is distinguished by content and structural features, forming part of the language lexical from the linguistic point of view. The methodology of teaching a foreign language is an integral part of linguodidactics and is thought about the importance of their linguistic features in the teaching of terms.*

Keywords: *terminology feature, lexical unit, methodology, didactics, lexical, component, technology, Foreign Language, English.*

Introduction. Scientific and philosophical interest in World linguistics in the XIX century increased the attention to the study of a specific language unit – terminology, which had a special terminological meaning, the reasons for this were the creation of terms and the inextricably linked with the influence of extralinguistic factors on terminology. As a result of the rapid growth of technical progress, industrial terminology is also formed in a unique way. This further explains the need for the study of sectoral terminology, its teaching in foreign languages, its comparative application in different languages, as well as the trends in the development of a specialist language.

Methodology. Today, the reforms carried out in the country's industrial systems are accelerating the flow of international terms entering the lexical level of the language. This situation dictates that the owners of the sphere have sufficient knowledge of the original essence and meaning of the terms and concepts related to their profession. The need to conduct scientific research on the techniques of translation of terms, especially in the railway sector, the semantic features of the terms in the railway sector, the comparison of the typological classification of terminology in different languages, linguistic analysis and teaching of translation problems, the

construction of terms in the railway sector with the help affixes and prefixes and their use terms are an important component of the language of Science and technology as a means of serving the formation of the product, principles, rules, laws, theories of the thinking activity of a person. Terms are a source of use not only for linguists, but also for specialists of various fields .¹

Wide application of the results of activities related to the direction of terminology opens further directions of the terminological sphere, allows setting new goals and tasks. In the scientific literature, various definitions of the term come from, for example, L.Krisin describes the term as follows: the lexeme "term" comes from the Latin word "terminus", meaning "end", "check", "limit", "end", V.N.Y.Shevchuk believes that the term "quot; - This is a word, which in the Middle Ages meant "define", "express". P.The note states that " the term is a word or a combination of words according to its structure, and in terms of semantics it is a lexical unit that is limited by the scope of a special field and expresses an understanding of this field."² There are many scientific classifications and descriptions of terms, which are considered from the point of view of the different aspects of the definition of concepts.³ These classifications are aimed at studying the linguistic features of terms on the basis of their formation properties, their systematization, their separation into specific types.

"The terms actually have a lexical-semantically generalized pattern, and they go through a specific terminological system to the common language. After all, terms and words in general are lexical units that complement each other . Thus, terminology is one of the factors shaping this language lexicon.

The formation of terminological systems, that is, terminology related to the railway sector, develops on the basis of language domestic capabilities and foreign languages. From other field terms, the terms related to the railway industry differ in their richness and practicality in application, as well as the use of certain syntactic expressions. The specific features of the terms related to the railway industry were determined on the basis of terminology nominations, linguistic features, requirements of the terminological lexicon.⁴

The structure and application of terms allows them to distinguish between the laws of general legalization, according to the methods of term formation, there are the following main criteria in the classification of terms used in the railway industry:

- 1) classification according to the spheres of social activity of science or society;

¹ Nishanov P. French and Northern languages of juridical terminology of typologic Tadei: Filol. fan. nom Diss. abstract. - Toshkent, 2009. 26 b.

² Shevchuk V.N. Derivatives of military terms in the English language. Moscow: 1983. 198 PP.

³ Krysin L.P. Explanatory dictionary of foreign words. Moscow: 1998. 503s.

⁴ Leychik V.M. On the question of the philosophical foundations of terminology / Branch terminology and its extralinguistic conditionality. Voronezh, 1986. Pp. 41-48.

2) classification taking into account the peculiarities of small systems within a large terminological system.

3) terminology expressionalydigan classification according to concepts;

4) classification according to the structure of the term;

5) classification according to the methods of making terminology;

6) according to the original National terms;

7) assimilation according to the terms;

8) according to hybrid terms.

Modern terminology bases of languages are composed of original national and borrowed terms. In the field of rail according to the frequency of application.

In future specialists, the study of the gnoseological composition of terms in the field of Railways in the formation of these features is the leading factor. "On the basis of the modern educational system, there is a planned, collaborative, result-oriented, socially significant activity. One of the main tasks of education is the creation of conditions for the development of educators through personal and socially significant activities.

Language and speech consist mainly of four hemispheres: phonetics-phonology, morphology, lexicology and syntax. In the literature on linguistics, morphology and syntax fields are called by one term – grammatics.¹

At the initial stage of the formation of professional speech skills, future specialists are introduced to the most basic features of the terms in the railway sector, and they are taught different aspects and interrelationships between them from other sectoral terms. In the educational process, the use of explanatory dictionaries, aimed at revealing the main features of the terms in the railway industry, occupies a leading place in the formation of professional speech skills. The terms of the railway industry are part of the terminological system, the terms of the industry: clearly reflect the direction of the sphere and the linguistic competences.

Also, terms related to the railway sector have a structural feature, they form hierarchical relations, that is, simple elements from complex elements, as well as in paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations enter into relations with other terms of the field.

In the educational process, it is desirable to use interactive techniques in the correct pronunciation of terms related to the railway sector, as well as in achieving memorization. The use of interactive techniques in increases the effectiveness of the lesson, mastering the pronunciation of terms related to the field. knowledge of these

¹ Irisqulov M.T. Tilshunoslikka kirish. Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2009. B. 42. .

terms, practical application, correct understanding and analysis will allow to strengthen.¹

In the present-day methodology, personality-oriented teaching is widely promoted, in which the main idea of teaching is the organization of classes taking into account the types of learning (auditory, visual and kinesthetic) as hearing, seeing and feeling that these methods of learning are considered. When planning lessons, it is planned to use an exercise system that will cover all the listed learning methods. It should be taken into account that the implementation of practical exercises and types of tasks certainly satisfy the needs of learners belonging to all methods.

It is important to pay special attention to the ability to pronounce the terms of the sphere in the training sessions, which makes it possible to develop the ability to use the terms of the sphere in professional communication to easily master the terms. The incorrect pronunciation of the sound in the field of terminology complicates the process of oral communication, which leads to a change in the meaning of the term, and this directly proves that phonetic skills have a feature of meaning differentiation. The use of interactive techniques in the educational process improves the ability to know, master, understand, analyze and practice the pronunciation of terms related to the railway sector.

At the next stage, future specialists will get acquainted with the meaning and features of the terms related to the railway sector, as well as the process of its application. In order to increase the effectiveness of the lesson, the materials must be adapted to its practical application before the student adapts to the method of learning. When teaching foreign languages is always in practical form and viewed from the point of view of the integration of current practice with the educational process, it is necessary to teach students the appearance of the language in Real life and enrich them with the skills they need in their professional and everyday life. The educational objectives corresponding to needs, interests and values increase their interest in the material under study.

Before explaining the meaning of terms related to the railway sector in the educational process, it is necessary to formulate first thoughts about the terminology, "the term should generally mean one in the dictionary of the specified language", "the term and its components are often used in one sense within the technical sciences". In the course of the lesson, visual perception, compliance of materials with the subject and proper application of individual approaches increase the possibility of future specialists to study the peculiarities and structuring characteristics of terms, compare different points of view, evaluate and draw conclusions.

¹ Leontiev A.N. Lectures on General psychology / Pod.ed. by D. A. Leontiev, E. E. Sokolova.M: Meaning. 2000. P. 4.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the use of interactive techniques in the process of teaching terms related to the railway sector will serve as a basis for improving the professional competence of future specialists. The training of qualified personnel in the field and the development of the field will contribute to the consistent study of the terms related to the railway sector. The relevance of the study of terms in the field of Railways is inextricably linked, mainly, with the development of International Relations, local and foreign cooperation, as well as with the increase in communication in this area, the activity of qualified personnel occupies a leading place in it.

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